

1 'Fire Islands': Holocene wildfire intensity as a critical determinant of carbon accumulation in
2 South Atlantic peatlands

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13 Abstract

14 Until recently, quantifying wildfire intensity in palaeoecological records has not been possible.
15 Therefore, little is known about the link between past wildfire intensity, carbon accumulation and
16 climate.

17 This study presents a history of burning and carbon accumulation spanning ~15,500 years across a peat
18 profile recovered from the Falkland Islands, including commonplace charcoal as evidence for frequent
19 natural burning since the onset of peat formation. Utilising Raman spectra of preserved macrocharcoal
20 fragments, we applied a recent cone calorimeter-based calibration to reconstruct changes in multi-fire
21 intensity. In the early Holocene, wetter local conditions are reflected in higher carbon accumulation
22 rates, variable charcoal fluxes, low burning intensities, and more diverse vegetation. Wildfire intensity
23 started to increase between 8000 and 6000 cal BP with maximum intensities between approx. 4000
24 and 1000 cal BP, while carbon accumulation rates constantly declined. These developments concur
25 with major changes in climate and in the position and strength of the southern westerly winds,
26 potentially desiccating biomass and fuelling combustion. Fuel availability and type due to peatland
27 succession processes also plays a role in wildfire intensity changes.

28 Our data show a strong negative correlation between burning intensities and carbon accumulation
29 rates and, strikingly, between burning intensity and charcoal flux. This demonstrates that high charcoal
30 fluxes are not necessarily equivalent to high fire intensities, and that the opposite might often be true.
31 Given the latter, we suggest caution to researchers extrapolating wildfire behaviour solely upon the
32 presence of macrocharcoal.

33

34 Keywords: Raman spectroscopy; Charcoal; Peat; Wildfire; Carbon accumulation

35 1. Introduction

36 Wildfires are impacting a wide range of ecosystems and the ever-expanding wildland-urban
37 interface. With escalating trends in frequency, area burned, and seasonal extent, they present a
38 globally growing concern (e.g. Nolan et al., 2022). Northern peatlands (Wilkinson et al., 2023) and
39 boreal forests (Kharuk et al., 2021) are particularly susceptible to wildfire disturbance under
40 accelerated warming and a changing climate, as elevated plant productivity and reductions in
41 underlying groundwater levels support the progressive drying of biomass, including sub-surface peat
42 deposits. This in turn supports larger, more intense wildfires, as well as lower intensity smouldering in
43 the sub-surface. As a global carbon sink that exceeds the sum of all living vegetation within just 3% of
44 the land surface, peatlands are at particular risk of releasing carbon stocks under escalating wildfire
45 regimes. In order to better understand and mitigate the consequences of wildfire activity upon carbon

46 accumulation in modern peatlands, we must consider the relationships between wildfire and
47 ecosystem functioning held within Holocene peatland records.

48 Southern Hemisphere peatlands are nowhere near as extensive as those in the Northern
49 Hemisphere, but nevertheless have the potential to provide long-term insights into wildfire and carbon
50 sequestration, particularly in the South Atlantic islands. Peat deposits in the Falkland Islands
51 (Malvinas), comprise ~50% of the total land area, some dating back to ~16,500 cal BP (Wilson et al.,
52 2002) with abundant charcoal fragments (Mauquoy et al., 2020). Evidence for pre-European
53 population on the Falkland Islands (1764 CE) is insecure (Zangrando and Borrero, 2022). Falkland
54 Islands' peatlands therefore offer the potential to reconstruct changes in natural wildfire activity on
55 centennial and millennial timescales, as an integral baseline for this environmental hazard.

56 Studies considering wildfire histories across both Northern and Southern peatlands often
57 remain constrained to volumetric (number, volume, concentration, accumulation rate, e.g. Davies et
58 al., 2023) or morphometric (char morphology or geometry) analyses of subfossil char records (Glückler
59 et al., 2022; Haliuc et al., 2023). These fail, ultimately, in reconstructing long-term changes in true
60 wildfire intensity (time-averaged energy flux in $W\ m^{-2}$; Keeley, 2009) as a key metric for the preheating
61 associated with a fire front, the consumption of fuels, and the rate of spread (Marcisz et al., 2019).
62 Existing methods in measuring wildfire intensity, fire number, and area burned, have been supported
63 by satellite imagery since 2001 (Justice et al., 2002). In contrast, tree-ring scars have offered a method
64 of recording wildfire incidence in the recent past (e.g., last few centuries) and estimating intensity
65 (Bergeron and Brisson, 1990). Both methods therefore have limited applicability in multi-millennial
66 reconstructions.

67 Sub-fossil charcoal deposits, as a means for quantitative wildfire intensity reconstruction,
68 remain underexplored. By application of transfer functions to a peat profile - in tandem with
69 macrocharcoal counts, satellite data (burned areas, fire numbers, intensity), and annual lacustrine
70 charcoal deposits (Adolf et al., 2018a, b) – Marcisz et al. (2019) evaluated the validity of a European
71 calibration dataset (Adolf et al., 2018a), concluding variabilities in fire activity were not sufficiently
72 characterised by macro- nor microcharcoal regression models. This was limited, in turn, by restricted
73 calibration windows for satellite data.

74 Constantine et al. (2023) applied FTIR spectroscopy to Australian lacustrine charcoals to
75 investigate wildfire “charring intensity” prior to- and following anthropogenic influence, based upon
76 experimental calibration results (Constantine et al., 2021). The applicability of this study was, however,
77 limited by use of laboratory oven-produced charcoals, unable to replicate the complexities of flaming
78 combustion as experienced in a wildfire. Furthermore, the application of integrated temperature and
79 time, as their primary fire metric, contrast the true measure of fire intensity as time-averaged energy
80 flux (Keeley, 2009).

81 Recent efforts in char-derived wildfire reconstruction have applied Raman spectroscopy and
82 cone calorimetry in tandem to peatland fuel mixes, modelling energy release (kJ) and total incident
83 energy (MW) as proxies for wildfire intensity (Theurer et al., 2024). Alongside typical volumetric and
84 morphometric techniques, this method of intensity reconstruction has revealed unique insights into
85 wildfire palaeoecology, including inferences of fire severity and fuel structure (Marcisz et al., 2025).

86 This research aims to integrate both established volumetric and novel spectroscopic
87 techniques in order to quantitatively reconstruct the intensity of Holocene wildfires recorded in a
88 Falkland Island peat profile. We seek to explore the interactions between peat carbon accumulation
89 rates, fire intensity, charcoal influx, peat-forming vegetation and climate changes recorded in the
90 archipelago (e.g. Thomas et al., 2018; Scaife et al., 2019; Monteath et al., 2022; Spoth et al., 2023;
91 Tamhane et al., 2023).

92 2. Methodology

93 2.1 Study area and sampling site

94 Our study site is within the Goose Green (GG) farm boundaries, situated centrally on the East
95 Falkland Islands, north of Choiseul Sound (Fig. 1). Annual mean temperatures range between 6 and
96 7°C, with less than 600 mm per year of precipitation and an average wind speed of 31 km h⁻¹. The study
97 site is a typical blanket peatland, dominated by species adapted to the harsh climate: *Cortaderia*
98 *egmontiana* (whitegrass), *Blechnum penna-marina*, *Baccharis magellanica*, *Empetrum rubrum*,
99 *Oreobolus obtusangulus*, *Gaultheria pumila*, *Myrteola nummularia* and *Anthoxanthum redolens*.

100

101 *Figure 1: a) The Falkland Islands and the sampling site on Goose Green farm on the east Falklands (light blue mark). b)*
102 *Sampling location, Cortaderia egmontiana-dominated peatland. c) C. egmontiana culm with spikelets. d) Deepest 50 cm*
103 *section of the Goose Green peat profile.*

104

105 2.2 Field sampling, Sample preparation and processing

106 Duplicate core profiles (GG-A and GG-B) were taken in 2022 at 51°49'08.7"S 58°48'10.2"W with
107 a stainless-steel Russian peat corer. The uppermost 50 cm were retrieved using a stainless-steel box
108 corer. The cores were wrapped in clingfilm, transferred into halved PVC-tubing, sealed for transport
109 and storage, and frozen at the University of Aberdeen. One charcoal sample from a recent fire
110 (February 2023) was collected from a proximal site.

111 The frozen peat profiles were cut contiguously into ~1.2 cm slices with a stainless-steel bone
112 band-saw, with dimensions and wet and dry mass then measured to calculate bulk densities. Dried

113 samples (n=159) were homogenised using a Retsch MM200 ball mill and 7.6 mg prepared for C:N-
 114 analysis on a Flash Combustion Elemental Analyser (CE Instruments NA 2500 Flash Combustion EA).
 115 Four cm³ of selected wet samples were warmed in 10% NaOH, gently rinsed with distilled water
 116 through a 180 µm mesh sieve, and stored in MilliQ-water. Macrocharcoal fragments and percentage
 117 components of macrofossils, grouped into *Sphagnum*, graminoids, dwarf shrubs and total remains
 118 (including other and unidentifiable remains), were counted under a stereo microscope using a 10 × 10
 119 cm grid.

120 For Raman spectroscopy, macrocharcoal fragments from ×56 samples were concentrated by
 121 pipetting off lighter non-charred material, manually inspected, cleaned and dried for 48 hours at 40°C.
 122 Using this method, thirteen out of these 56 had already been presented in Theurer et al. (2024).

123

124 2.3 Radiocarbon dating and age-depth modelling

125 Nine samples were prepared for AMS ¹⁴C dating. Samples were disaggregated and inspected
 126 under low-powered microscopy before being prepared for AMS ¹⁴C dating at the ¹⁴CHRONO Centre at
 127 Queen’s University Belfast. Macrofossil samples were picked from sieved sample material, carefully
 128 removing roots and fungal remains. The sample composition and the ¹⁴C dating results are presented
 129 in Supplementary Table S1. Chronologies were modelled using a Bayesian approach implemented in
 130 rbacon version 3.5.2 in R (Blaauw and Christen, 2011) based on the SHCal20 calibration curve (Hogg et
 131 al., 2020). The sampling year 2022 CE was assigned to the core’s surface.

132

133 2.4 Raman spectroscopy and data processing

134 Raman spectroscopic analysis was applied (n=25 per sample) to randomised positions across
 135 each macrocharcoal fragment (see above) exhibiting high surface reflectance (Theurer et al., 2024).
 136 Details of spectroscopic hardware and setup parameters are outlined in Tab. 2 after Theurer et al.
 137 (2025). The application here of Raman spectroscopy to charcoal fragments remains consistent with
 138 established protocols in the reconstruction of wildfire activity, specific to peatland environments
 139 (Mauquoy et al., 2020; Theurer et al., 2021; 2022; 2024). Following the method developed by Theurer
 140 et al. (2024), coded auto-deconvolution (*after* Schito and Corrado, 2020) was applied to the derivation
 141 of Raman band separation values (‘RBS’) from ‘G- and D-band’ positions. Increases in these values are
 142 attributable to an increase in both total incident energy and the energy released by flaming
 143 combustion (Theurer et al., 2024) across any mix of peatland fuels. Therefore, as a direct measure of
 144 energy flux within fuels during wildfire, the application of Raman spectroscopy here remains consistent
 145 with the reconstruction of true wildfire intensity (Keeley, 2009).

146 *Table 1: Details of the hardware, software, and protocols applied to calibration and deconvolution of spectra during Raman*
 147 *spectroscopic analysis, as applied to this study (after Theurer et al., 2025).*

Component	Sub-component	Details
Sample	Pre-treatment	Dried for 48 hours at 40°C
Spectrometer	Model	Renishaw ‘InVia Reflex’ Raman spectrometer
Microscope	Model	Leica DM2700M
	Objective Magnification	×50
Laser	Source	Green diode-pumped (Cobalt)
	Wavelength	514.5 nm
	Applied Power	<0.3 mW (1% Total output)
	Spot Size	1 – 2 µm
Calibration	Reference Peak	Silicon (520.5 cm ⁻¹)
	Reference Offset	As required

	Beamsteer	As required
Spectral Acquisition & Deconvolution	Grating	2400 l/mm (Visible spectrum)
	Static Scan Centre	1400 cm ⁻¹
	Scan Range/s	~1100 – 1700 cm ⁻¹
	Scan Resolution	~3 cm ⁻¹
	Additional Functions	Cosmic ray removal
	N ^o . Acquisitions	3
	Duration of Exposure	5s per acquisition
	Baseline Subtraction	Linear
	Curve Fit	Pseudo-Voigt (50% Gaussian-Lorentzian Hybrid)
	No. Curves	2 ('D' and 'G')

148

149 2.5 Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

150 A principal component analysis (PCA) was performed in R using the package *prcomp* and
151 visualised using *corrplot*.

152

153 3. Results and Discussion

154 Radiocarbon dating of near-basal samples suggest an onset of peat accumulation in Goose
155 Green, Falkland Islands, at approx. 16,000 cal BP (Tab. 2), with a maximum accumulation rate (0.4 mm
156 yr⁻¹) between 12,500—9000 cal BP, transitioning into lower accumulation rates below 0.2 mm yr⁻¹,
157 persisting until recent centuries (Fig. 2).

158 *Table 2: Radiocarbon dates with ¹⁴C-ages and F¹⁴C. *published in Theurer et al. (2024).*

Lab. No.	Sample-ID	Depth [cm]	Material	¹⁴ C-age [BP]	F ¹⁴ C
UBA-50630	GG1A-14	16.8	Charred macrofossils	184 ± 21	0.9773 ± 0.0026
UBA-49616	GG1A 39	48.0	Charred leaf bases and stems	2565 ± 21	0.7266 ± 0.0019
UBA-44798	GG1B-29	75.4	Charred macrofossils	4539 ± 37	0.5684 ± 0.0026
UBA-50362	GG1A 56	97.4	Charred leaf bases and stems	5731 ± 29	0.49 ± 0.0018
UBA-44799	GG1B-50	129.4	Charred macrofossils	7309 ± 39	0.4026 ± 0.002
UBA-50631	GG1B-76	161.7	Charred macrofossils	8299 ± 38	0.3559 ± 0.0017
UBA-49618	GG1B 110	192.9	<i>Sphagnum magellanicum</i>	9737 ± 42	0.2976 ± 0.0015
UBA-50363	GG1B 134	253.4	Charred leaf bases and stems, Poaceae seeds	10607 ± 46	0.267 ± 0.0015
UBA- 49617*	GG1A 205	345.5	Charred leaf bases and stems	12485 ± 50	0.2114 ± 0.0013

Figure 2: Age-depth model produced in R with rbacon-package. Radiocarbon age of H1 eruption (in pink, add reference) added but not included in the model.

159 The inclusion of char fragments throughout this record offers a unique insight into full
 160 Holocene wildfire activity in a Southern Hemisphere peatland, independent of anthropogenic
 161 influence. Considering first the influx of macrocharcoal across this record (Fig. 3), a significant
 162 variability is observed within the earliest half, with values fluctuating between 0 and >350 pieces cm⁻²
 163 yr⁻¹ prior to 7800 cal BP. After 7800 cal BP, macrocharcoal influx stabilises at <50 pieces cm⁻² yr⁻¹.
 164 Substantial charcoal influx between ~12,200–11,600 cal BP, and again at 10,500 cal BP, coincide with
 165 disappearances of *Sphagnum* as an indication of drier conditions and greater fuel availability. Carbon
 166 accumulation rates record a maximum between c.12,500–9500 cal BP, with a rather steep decline
 167 from over 30 to less than 20 g C m⁻² yr⁻¹ up to 7800 cal BP, continuing to decline to around 10 g C m⁻²
 168 yr⁻¹ until 300 cal BP. Raman-derived wildfire energy release (i.e. intensity), exhibits a near-antithetical
 169 behaviour. Initially fluctuating between 130–165 kJ until c.8000 cal BP, an increasing trend culminates
 170 at maxima of c.190 kJ between 3600–3100, and again between 1700–1300 cal BP, before dropping
 171 below 160 kJ in the recent past.

Figure 3: Profiles of charcoal influx [$n/cm^2 \cdot a$], carbon accumulation rate [$g/(cm^2 \cdot a)$], energy release [kJ], total macrofossil remains [%] and macrofossil percentages (*Sphagnum*=green, *graminoids*=yellow, *dwarf shrubs*=red).

173 PCA of fire and ecological metrics emphasise underlying relationships in key areas of wildfire
 174 behaviour, char generation, and carbon accumulation. PC1 (42.8% of variance) shows a general linkage
 175 between increasing wildfire energy release, decreasing charcoal flux and carbon accumulation rates,
 176 and changes in plant community composition (Fig. 5). The positive correlation between energy release
 177 and dwarf shrubs is expected, as woody material generally provides greater mass, and calorific
 178 content, compared to graminoids. This may, however, be influenced by the propensity of dwarf shrub-
 179 dominated communities to higher-intensity wildfire, supported in turn by an aerated canopy, further
 180 susceptible to moisture vapour deficits. In kind, greater fire intensities likely readily combust graminoid
 181 materials, generating gaseous components, or ash and microcharcoals subsequently lost during
 182 sieving.

183 PC2 (15.1% of variance) demonstrates that periods of *Sphagnum* dominance coincide with a reduction
 184 in charcoal influx. Not only indicating more humid conditions, these environments are clearly also poor
 185 in above-ground biomass (fuel). This would limit, primarily, opportunities for ignition, but also act to
 186 reduce the intensity and duration of fires that initiate on-site or spread onto the site from surrounding,
 187 drier slopes. In drier environments, such as the 'whitegrass' peatlands typical to the Falkland Islands,
 188 burning is expected to occur closer to the soil as dry fuels burn in entirety, and any charred or burning
 189 material would likely smoulder and retain heat for a longer time at the soil surface. Since peat-forming
 190 *Sphagnum* mosses can be vulnerable to more severe fire activity (Noble et al., 2019), periods of
 191 repeated burning potentially eradicated *Sphagnum* communities present between 13,000—10,000 cal
 192 BP (Fig. 4), slowly released nutrients favouring vascular plants, and ultimately reduced carbon
 193 accumulation.

194

195 *Figure 4: Correlation matrix of principal components and selected variables.*

196 It is therefore evident that wildfire represents a pervasive key ecological process at the study
 197 site, both sculpting and sculpted by vegetational change, in turn governing the production and
 198 incorporation of charcoal as a key determinant of carbon accumulation. Indeed, high fire frequency
 199 has been observed in previous studies on the Falkland Islands (Mauquoy et al., 2020), though
 200 seemingly limited to particular periods (Thomas et al., 2018; Scaife et al., 2019; Groff et al., 2020).
 201 Contrastingly, our record demonstrates that burning was and is a near permanent factor in this
 202 environment.

203 The observed threshold in high-low charcoal influx around 7800 cal BP is consistent with a
 204 transition in the behaviour of Southern Westerly Winds (SWW) in this region. According to Perren et
 205 al. (2025), the SWW were stronger and positioned further south than today between 10,000–7500
 206 cal BP, identifying the resultant conditions as analogous to future warmer climate scenarios.
 207 Positioning of the SWW to the south of the Falklands resulted in lower wind strength and warmer
 208 temperatures on the islands, as suggested for the period ~11,000–6000 cal BP (Spoth et al., 2022;
 209 Tamhane et al., 2023). After wetter periods (12,200–11,000 cal BP and 10,000–8000 cal BP), Scaife et
 210 al. (2019) suggest a shift to drier conditions from 8200–6450 cal BP. Largely overlapping with this time
 211 window, Groff et al. (2020) observe increasing charcoal accumulation rates.

212 It is during the presumably calmer, warmer, and wetter period between 10,000–8000 cal BP,
 213 that the Goose Green profile records a preliminary increase in the influx of charcoal and the beginning
 214 of a slow decline in peat and carbon accumulation rates. Concurrently, the permanent disappearance
 215 of *Sphagnum* suggests a shift to a more fire prone state. In the warmer and drier conditions succeeding
 216 8000 cal BP, there is a significant congruent fall in carbon accumulation from c.25 to below 15 g C m⁻²
 217 yr⁻¹ and a significant increase in fire intensity.

218 Several studies concur on a transition to wetter, cooler and partly stormier conditions, initiated
 219 between 6900–5500 cal BP and persisting until at least 2500 cal BP (Thomas et al., 2018; Spoth et al.,
 220 2023, Tamhane et al., 2023, Groff et al., 2020). Moreno et al. (2018) see strong SWW since 7500 cal BP
 221 and a shift to wet/cold intervals after 5800 cal BP at 51°S in Patagonia. Whilst wildfire intensity
 222 increased to maximum levels during this period, wetter conditions do not seem to have induced major
 223 fluctuations in vegetation visible in our record, nor in charcoal flux or carbon accumulation at our site.
 224 Instead, charcoal influx and carbon and peat accumulation rates decreased further. This could be due
 225 to the resilience of Falklands' grass and dwarf shrub communities to temperature changes of ~1°C
 226 (Bokhorst et al., 2007), and to the increasing distance of surface vegetation to the water table. The
 227 effect of increased SWW strength likely overcompensated cooler and wetter conditions after approx.

228 6000 cal BP, recurrently desiccating increased superficial biomass leading to fire intensification by
229 providing aeration and fire propagation.

230 A higher intensity of the SWW is suggested by Tamhane et al. (2023) from 3000—1700 cal BP,
231 parallel to an eastward extension of the Amundsen Sea Low, leading to drier conditions that are
232 conducive to both maximum fire intensity (energy release) and the lowest rates of carbon
233 accumulation. A transition to a drier and warmer climate after 2500 cal BP (Thomas et al., 2018) and
234 Atlantic sea surface warming at 50°S since 2000 cal BP (Nielsen et al., 2004) correlate with the
235 decreasing burning intensity in our record since c.1700 cal BP to levels prevailing prior to 8000 BP. Such
236 a pronounced change could have caused vegetation cover and biomass reduction (i.e. fuel availability),
237 which, especially under low precipitation and low water table, would have induced lower fire
238 intensities. Removal of fuel by the introduction of livestock and prescribed burning by European
239 settlers since the late 18th century (Armstrong, 1994) likely explains why the intensity is still decreasing,
240 unlike the increase of fire intensity in response to a drier phase after 8000 cal BP.

241

242 4. Conclusions

243 In our detailed palaeo-record of quantitative wildfire intensity and fire frequency in a Falkland
244 Islands' peatland, variable but wetter environments in the late Pleistocene and early Holocene show
245 less complete combustion, reflected in higher charcoal influx and lower fire intensities, resulting in
246 greater peat and carbon accumulation. Generally, the observed changes in the wildfire regimes,
247 vegetation, carbon accumulation and charcoal flux could be driven by changing temperatures,
248 precipitation, and mostly by the position and strength of the SWW.

249 We observe a transition to burning intensification and lower carbon accumulation after the
250 early Holocene, in an initial response to at first warmer and then also drier conditions after 8000 cal
251 BP. Counter-intuitively, colder and wetter but windier conditions at ~6000 cal BP likely generated even
252 more intense fires, reaching maxima between 4000 and 1000 cal BP. Firstly, by increasing fuel
253 production and secondly, natural succession may have shifted vegetation communities to those more
254 prone to intense burning, especially under strong desiccating winds, which also fan the flames. The
255 commonplace condition of Falkland Islands' peatlands as dry, and at a mature stage of succession,
256 suggests that their carbon stocks are under escalating, co-interacting pressures from climate change,
257 grazing, prescribed burning, and natural fires.

258 The observed relationship between carbon accumulation rate and fire intensity is strongly
259 negative, controlled by the types of peat forming vegetation, natural succession, and climatic changes
260 through time.

261 Strikingly, the relationship between charcoal flux and fire intensity in our study is also clearly
262 negative. Hence, lower charcoal fluxes do not necessarily mean fewer or less extensive fire activity.
263 Instead, they can result from charcoal consumption during combustion under higher intensities,
264 generating ash and gases. This is a key finding calling for further research, as most wildfire
265 reconstructions tend to rely upon charcoal counts, concentration, or flux calculations only. The
266 addition of a fire intensity proxy offers a detailed and nuanced method to understand the behaviour
267 of wildfires across extensive and variable time scales.

268

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273
274 Authors contributions
275 **Dmitri Mauquoy:** Fieldwork, Project administration, Conceptualisation, Supervision, Writing-
276 Original draft preparation, Writing- Reviewing and Editing, Funding acquisition.: **Clemens von Scheffer:**
277 Fieldwork, Investigation, Data curation, Writing- Original draft preparation, Project administration,
278 Visualisation, Conceptualisation, Methodology, Funding acquisition. **Thomas Theurer:** Fieldwork,
279 Methodology, Writing- Reviewing and Editing, Funding acquisition.: **Daniel Coathup:** Sample
280 preparation, Writing- Reviewing and Editing. **David Muirhead:** Funding acquisition, Methodology,
281 Writing- Reviewing and Editing.

282
283

284 Declaration of competing interests

285 We declare that there is no conflict of interest.

286

287 Data availability

288 All relevant data will be uploaded on zenodo (link will follow after acceptance) in addition to the
289 information and data supplementary to this manuscript.

290

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